

Analysis of hydraulic behavior in pressurized systems with different automation mechanisms using Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft sets

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Abstract. Residential pressurization has significantly influenced energy consumption, particularly in systems with low-power pumps. Therefore, this study assessed the hydraulic and energy performance of three configurations: a centrifugal pump with presscontrol, a hydropneumatic system, and a hybrid system, structured using Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets. The results indicated that the presscontrol system exhibited the highest efficiency (22.48%), followed by the hybrid system (21.62%) and the hydropneumatic system (20.17%), with minimal differences in operational flow rates. It was concluded that although these systems do not meet high-demand scenarios, they are efficient for most common sanitary fixtures, optimizing energy consumption and sustainability in residential and industrial environments. Future studies are recommended to evaluate attributes with varying degrees of neutrosophic membership to validate their technical, economic, and environmental feasibility under different demand conditions.

Keywords: Hydraulic performance, Energy efficiency, Technical evaluation, Residential hydraulic systems, Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft sets.

1 Introduction

Residential pumping systems are a significant component of residential energy consumption, primarily due to their low operational efficiency, which in many cases does not exceed 20%. This inefficiency is often addressed through technical regulations and energy assessments aimed at guiding corrective actions such as equipment repair or replacement [1]. Various studies have demonstrated that energy efficiency depends on factors such as dynamic flow, the thermal inertia of materials, and the proper selection of pumps with optimal efficiency rates between 50% and 60% [2]. Exergy evaluation enables the identification of energy losses in both residential and industrial systems.

Therefore, traditional pumping station designs are typically based on multiple parameters, whereas more recent methodologies propose multicriteria analysis [3]. These approaches incorporate technical, economic, and environmental factors, thereby improving equipment selection and system efficiency under varying operational conditions [4]. Consequently, in areas where water pressure is insufficient due to factors such as topography or the distance between residences and reservoirs, pressurization systems become convenient. In fact, these systems are designed to maintain and regulate pressure in distribution networks. A common type employs a pressure switch combined with a hydropneumatic tank, which maintains pressure within a specific range and controls flow according to demand. However, such systems often exhibit failures, such as dry running, which occurs when water is absent in the pipeline, yet the pressure switch activates the pump due to low pressure, potentially damaging the

motor.

Given this situation, the present study evaluated the hydraulic and energy performance of residential pressurization systems using a 0.5 HP centrifugal pump in three configurations: presscontrol, dropneumatic system, and a hybrid system. The research aims to assess these systems' parameters through a structured analysis employing Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets under different power sets across technical, economic, environmental, and operational-contextual dimensions. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets modeling enables the integration of multiple attributes to optimize each evaluated parameter or parameter pair. Ultimately, this work advances the development of more reliable and efficient pressurization systems with applications in residential, commercial, and industrial environments [5].

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets.

This section serves the purpose of remembering the basic notions of Fuzzy Extension SuperHyperSoft Sets and neutrosophic theory [6].

Definition 1 ([1, 9, 10]). Given U is the initial universe set and E is the set of parameters. A pair (F, E) is called a *soft set* (over U) if and only if F is a mapping of E into the set of all subsets of U .

That is to say, having a set E of parameters and fixing a parameter $\varepsilon \in E$, then $F(\varepsilon) \in \mathcal{P}(U)$, where $\mathcal{P}(U)$ denotes the power set of U and $F(\varepsilon)$ is considered the set of ε -elements of the Soft Set (F, E) or the set of ε -approximate elements of the Soft Set [7] [8].

It is not difficult to realize that fuzzy sets are soft sets, this is a consequence of the α -levels definition of a membership function μ_A , which yields the following:

$F(\alpha) = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) \geq \alpha\}$, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. Thus, if the family F is known, then the function μ_A may be derived using the following formula:

$$\mu_A(x) = \sup_{\substack{\alpha \in [0, 1] \\ x \in F(\alpha)}} \alpha$$

Thus, a fuzzy set is a $(F, [0, 1])$ soft set.

Given a binary operation $*$ for subsets of the set U , where (F, A) and (G, B) are soft sets over U . Then, the operation $*$ for soft sets is defined as follows:

$(F, A) * (G, B) = (J, A \times B)$, where $J(\alpha, \beta) = F(\alpha) * G(\beta)$; $\alpha \in A$, $\beta \in B$, and $A \times B$ is the Cartesian product of the sets A and B .

Definition 2 ([2, 3, 11, 12]). Let U be a universe set, $\mathcal{P}(U)$ the power set of U . Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , for $n \geq 1$, be n distinct attributes, whose corresponding attribute values are respectively the sets A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n , with $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$, for $i \neq j$, and $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then the pair $(F, A_1 \times A_2 \times \dots \times A_n)$, where: $F: A_1 \times A_2 \times \dots \times A_n \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(U)$ is called a *HyperSoft Set* over U .

Definition 3 ([2, 3, 11, 12]). Let U be a universe set, $\mathcal{P}(U)$ the power set of U . Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , for $n \geq 1$, be n distinct attributes, whose corresponding attribute values are respectively the sets A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n , with $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$, for $i \neq j$, and $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then the pair $(F, \mathcal{P}(A_1) \times \mathcal{P}(A_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(A_n))$, where:

$F: \mathcal{P}(A_1) \times \mathcal{P}(A_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(A_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(U)$ is called a *SuperHyperSoft Set* over U .

Definition 4 ([4, 5, 13-15]). Let U be a universe set, $\mathcal{P}(U)$ the power set of U . Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , for $n \geq 1$, be n distinct attributes, whose corresponding attribute values are respectively the sets A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n , with $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$, for $i \neq j$, and $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then the pair $(F, \mathcal{P}(A_1) \times \mathcal{P}(A_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(A_n))$, where:

$F: \mathcal{P}(A_1) \times \mathcal{P}(A_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(A_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(U(x(d^0)))$ is called a *Fuzzy Extension SuperHyperSoft Set* over U .

Where $x(d^0)$ is the fuzzy or any fuzzy extension degree of appurtenance of the element x to the set U . Fuzzy extension means Fuzzy Set or Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set, Pythagorean Fuzzy Set, Fermatean Fuzzy Set, Neutrosophic Fuzzy Set, Plithogenic Fuzzy Set, etc [9].

Before concluding, let us recall some fundamental definitions of neutrosophic sets:

Definition 5 ([8]). The *Neutrosophic set* N is characterized by three membership functions [10], which are the truth-membership function T_A , indeterminacy-membership function I_A , and falsity-membership function F_A , where U is the Universe of Discourse and $\forall x \in U, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in]-0, 1+[$, and $-0 \leq \inf T_A(x) + \inf I_A(x) + \inf F_A(x) \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^+$ [11].

See that according to the definition, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or non-standard subsets of $] -0, 1+[$ and hence, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ can be sub-intervals of $[0, 1]$. -0 and 1^+ belong to the set of hyperreal numbers.

Definition 6 ([8, 16, 17]). The *Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set* (SVNS) A over U is $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$, where $T_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $F_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$. $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$.

2.2 Equipment, materials, and methods for calculating the selected parameters

The materials used in this research are listed in Table 1, where the equipment and materials are described along with their characteristics and a visual record of each item.

Table 1: Equipment and materials used. Source: own elaboration.

Items	Characteristics	Figure
INGCO UVPM3708 Peripheral Pump	This is a special type of rotodynamic pump (see Figure 1), characterized by its ability to handle high head at a low flow rate. The specifications of the peripheral pump are presented in Table 2.	
Pressure Switch	This is an electromechanical-type electrical switch (see Figure 2). The 3781 water pressure switch comes factory-set with the following default values: Cut-in pressure: 4.9 bar (± 0.3 bar), Cut-off pressure: 7.0 bar (± 0.3 bar), Maximum ΔP : 2.1 bar. Additional specifications of the pressure switch are presented in Table 3.	
Presscontrol	The presscontrol device (see Figure 3) is designed to automatically regulate and control water pressure in hydraulic systems. It detects malfunctions and signals them via a red indicator (alarm), subsequently shutting off the pump to prevent damage caused by dry operation. The specifications of the presscontrol device are presented in Table 3 [12].	

Figure 1: INGCO UVPM3708 Peripheral Pump.

Figure 2: 3781 Water Pressure Switch.

Hydropneumatic Tank These tanks contain compressed air and water; the compressed air acts as a spring that maintains constant pressure within the system by compensating for pressure fluctuations and ensuring stable flow (see Figure 4). The specifications of the 24-liter horizontal tank are presented in Table 3.

Figure 3: Presscontrol.

Figure 4: 24-Liter Horizontal Tank AQ24LH/AC with Carbon Steel Pump Base.

Flexible hose This corrugated metal hose (see Figure 5) is flexible, corrosion-resistant, and offers high temperature resistance. It has a length of 60 centimeters, a one-inch male thread, and a one-inch female thread.

Figure 5: Flexible metal hose.

Five-Way Coupling This is a bronze coupling with five distribution ports, featuring one-inch male and female threads, as well as male and female threads for connecting a pressure gauge and a pressure switch (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Five-Way Bronze Coupling.

Pressure Gauge This instrument is used to quantify the pressure level of fluids within a closed circuit (see Figure 7). It measures the difference between the actual or absolute pressure and atmospheric pressure, which is referred to as gauge pressure.

Figure 7: Pressure Gauge from 0 to 100 Psi.

Mesh-Type Network Module with Water Flow This experimental module is designed to validate simulations of mesh-type networks in the fluid laboratory at the Technical University of Cotopaxi. It consists of half-inch, one-inch, and one-and-a-half-inch pipes, ball valves, pressure sensors, and a control panel that integrates: a Siemens 1200 PLC, Siemens HMI, 24V power supply, contactor, motor protection switch, position selector, and pilot light, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Mesh-Type Network Module with Water Flow from the Fluid Laboratory of the Technical University of Cotopaxi.

Portable Ultrasonic Flow Meter This device has the capability to continuously monitor flow in hydraulic systems. The handheld TDS-100H ultrasonic flow meter (see Figure 9) is a battery-powered ultrasonic flow meter with the following specifications: accuracy better than 1%, 0.2% repeatability, LCD display with 4 lines of 16 English characters, operates with clamp-on transducers, RS-232 interface or isolated single-channel OCT output, pipe diameters ranging from 15 mm to 6000 mm, Ni-MH battery operation exceeding 12 hours, 90–230 VAC power supply, and internal data logging.

Figure 9: TDS-100H Handheld Ultrasonic Flow Meter.

Table 2: Specifications of the INGCO UVPM3708 0.5 HP pump. Source: <https://www.ingco.com/product/water-pump/VPM3708>.

Model No.	UVPM3708
Rated Voltage (V)	110-120~
Rated Frequency (Hz)	60
Phase	Single
Rated Output (kW / HP)	0,37 / 0,5
No-load Speed (rpm)	3450
Max. Head (m)	35
Max. Suction (m)	8
Max. Flow (l/min)	35
Inlet / Outlet (inches)	1x1

Table 3: Specifications of the 3781 pressure switch, presscontrol, and AQ24LH/AC Hydropneumatic tank. Source: own elaboration.

3781 Pressure switch		Presscontrol		AQ24LH/AC hydropneumatic tank	
Parameters	Magnitude	Parameters	Magnitude	Parameters	Magnitude
IP	64	Single-phase supply voltage	230V	Capacity L/gal	24/6,3
Connection voltage (V)	230	Frequency	50-60Hz	System	Interchangeable EPDM membrane
Maximum current consumption (A)	12	Maximum current	10(6)A	Maximum working pressure (Psi)	86
Maximum power (HP)	2	Protection rating	IP65	Maximum working temperature (°C)	99
Maximum pressure (Bar)	10	Maximum service pressure	10Bar	Precharge pressure (psi / bar)	21/1,5
Regulation range (Bar)	4 a 10	Maximum temperature in service	60°C	Male NPT connection diameter (inches)	1
Maximum ΔP (Bar)	2,1	Connections	1st Male		
Maximum frequency (cycles/min)	60	Maximum power	1,5 C.V.		
Mechanical life cycle	200000				
Electrical life cycle	30000				
Differential	Variable				
Maximum temperature (°C)	50				

2.3 Minimum instantaneous flow rates according to NEC11 standard

Table 16.1 of flow demand, pressure, and diameters in consumption devices is presented in (Ministry of Urban Development and Housing, 2011). Since the minimum flow rate in the table, according to the standard, is given in L/s, a unit conversion to m³/h was performed, resulting in Table 4.

Table 4: Flow demand in cubic meters per hour. Source: own elaboration.

Sanitary fixture	Minimum instantaneous flow rate (m ³ /h)	Head pressure height (m)
Bathtub	1.08	7.0
Bidet	0.36	7.0
Water heaters / boilers	1.08	15.0
Shower	0.72	10.0
Kitchen sink	0.72	5.0
Drinking fountains	0.36	3.0
Hose bib	0.72	7.0
Toilet with tank	0.36	7.0
Flush-valve toilet	4.5	15.0
Washbasin	0.36	5.0
Washing machine	0.72	7.0
Dishwasher	0.72	7.0
Flush-valve urinal	1.08	15.0
Manual-flush urinal	0.54	7.0
Sauna, steam bath, or domestic whirlpool bath	3.6	15.0

2.4 Equations and mathematical content

Calculation of Head Height (m): This equation determines the water column height based on a given pressure (1).

$$H = \frac{P}{\rho \cdot g} \tag{1}$$

Where, H = head height (m), P = pressure (Pa), ρ = fluid density (kg/m³), and g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s²).

Unit Conversion – Flow Rate: This conversion was used to express the volumetric flow rate measured in cubic meters per minute on an hourly scale. Additionally, a conversion from cubic meters per minute to cubic meters per second was performed to facilitate a better analysis of the data (2) (3).

$$Q' = Q \cdot 60 \quad \text{Flow rate calculation } Q \text{ (m}^3\text{/min)} \tag{2}$$

$$Q'' = \frac{Q}{60 \text{ seg}} \quad \text{Flow rate calculation } Q'' \text{ (m}^3\text{/s)} \tag{3}$$

Calculation of Electrical Power: This relation was used to determine the electrical power consumed by all systems based on voltage and current measurements (4).

$$P = V \cdot I \tag{4}$$

P = Electrical power (W)
V = Voltage (V)
I = Current (A)

Calculation of Hydraulic Power: This equation enabled the quantification of the hydraulic energy delivered by each system, considering the inlet pressure and the generated flow rate (5).

$$P_h = p_{in} \cdot Q'' \tag{5}$$

P_h = Hydraulic power (W)
 p_{in} = Inlet pressure (Pa)
 Q'' = Flow rate (m³/s)

Efficiency Calculation: This formula was applied to evaluate the efficiency of all systems by comparing the useful hydraulic power with the electrical power consumed (6).

$$\eta = \left(\frac{P_h}{P_e}\right) \cdot 100\% \quad \begin{array}{l} \eta = \text{System efficiency (\%)} \\ P_h = \text{Hydraulic power (W)} \\ P_e = \text{Electrical power (W)} \end{array} \quad (6)$$

PSI to Pascal Conversion Factor: This conversion was necessary to calculate the head without unit inconsistencies by transforming pressure from the International System of Units (SI), psi, to pascals (7)

$$p_{Pa} = p_{Psi} \cdot 6894,76 \quad \begin{array}{l} p_{Pa} = \text{Pressure in Pascals} \\ p_{Psi} = \text{Pressure in Psi} \end{array} \quad (7)$$

Error Calculation: This equation was used to determine the percentage deviation between the head height of each pressurization system and the actual head provided by the pump (8).

$$ERROR = \frac{H_S - H_B}{H_S} \cdot 100 \quad \begin{array}{l} ERROR = \text{Error (\%)} \\ H_S = \text{Head height of the evaluated system (m)} \\ H_B = \text{Head height of the pump (m)} \end{array} \quad (8)$$

3 Results

3.1 Designs, projects, and equipment acquisition and installation

Engineering projects constitute the means by which the desired states of the clients are transformed into concrete solutions, encompassing interventions ranging from small-scale residential works to mega-projects of transnational and intercontinental scope. Each project involves varying levels of complexity resulting from the interaction of multiple disciplines such as mechanical, hydraulic, process, civil, electrical, and automation engineering, among others. These projects enable the evaluation of designs and the measurement of quantifiable variables to ensure operation within their respective efficiency zones and to guarantee project success. Additionally, both complete data obtained through simulations and partial or indeterminate data, which often have decisive influence, must be considered. In this context, Neutrosophy provides an analytical tool to identify and classify parameter sets based on the client's desired state. For this purpose, the analysis is structured in the form of sets by organizing variables or attributes as power sets grouped into four main categories for this study:

- Power set of technical variables (A_i), where $(G, \mathcal{P}(A_1) \times \mathcal{P}(A_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(A_m))$
- Power set of economic variables (B_i), where $(G, \mathcal{P}(B_1) \times \mathcal{P}(B_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(B_n))$
- Power set of environmental variables (C_i), where $(G, \mathcal{P}(C_1) \times \mathcal{P}(C_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(C_p))$
- Power set of contextual and operational variables (D_i), where $(G, \mathcal{P}(D_1) \times \mathcal{P}(D_2) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}(D_q))$

Therefore, each power set is composed of a group of pairs, since each project does not incorporate all technical variables but only uses a certain number of pairs within this set according to the client's requirements or desires. For the purpose of this study, *the client's desire* is termed the *service request (SR)*, while the *client's requirement* is defined as the *technical or projection task (TT)*. Once these two elements are defined, in the following pair $E: \{\{SS\}, \{TT\}\}$, each project can be identified by the following function:

$$f(E) \rightarrow \{\{A_i\} \cap \{B_i\} \cap \{C_i\} \cap \{D_i\}\}$$

For example, in an industrial installation requiring a pumping system, the client must provide a service request along with a technical task specifying the site conditions. This allows the project engineer or designer to determine which equipment and materials should be selected based on the simulated technical parameters $\{A_1\}$. Similarly, the selection of equipment is conditioned by economic variables $\{B_i\}$ and their structures formed by pairs as follows:

- $\{\{Installation\ costs\}, \{Local\ electricity\ rates\}, \{Maintenance\ costs\}, \{Life\ cycle\ cost - benefit\}\}$.

Likewise, the {water reservoirs} and their {environmental impact} on the ecosystem must be defined as neutrosophic pairs that are either fully or partially defined. Similarly, an intersection with the power set D_k may or may not coexist. In this case, it is observed that the inclusion of multiple pairs allows for defining and fulfilling the client's needs as determined in $\{E\}$, which possesses characteristics that are fully defined, partially defined, or indeterminate. Therefore, the pairs can be defined, partially defined, or undefined within the power set to which they belong. In fact, an element acting on these pairs is the experience of both the client and the designer or project engineer. Consequently, experience constitutes an element identified in multiple neutrosophic states (high experience, medium experience, low experience, little experience, and no experience). These neutrosophic states are present in each power set, represented, for example, as $(x_{b_i}(d^0))$ in the following pair function:

$$F(a_i \cap b_i) = \{P_i\}, \{(x_{a_i}(d^0)) \cap (x_{b_i}(d^0))\}$$

Therefore, each pair in the function is assigned a neutrosophic membership degree, which is determined by the level of knowledge and experience of both the client and the project engineer or designer. Thus, if the client has little experience, the parameter pairs found in $\{E\}$ would be classified as partially defined or undefined for certain domains. For example, if the client commissions a project defining a set of technical, environmental, and operational parameters in $\{E\}$, but only partially defines the economic parameters, then the resulting intersection $\{A_i\} \cap \{B_i\} \cap \{C_i\} \cap \{D_i\}$ would exhibit a neutrosophic degree that is partially indeterminate. In this case, the outcome could be a project solution that satisfies $\{A_i\} \cap \{C_i\} \cap \{D_i\}$, but might be very costly, and the client would lack funding to execute it. Therefore, the partial omission of economic variable parameters would compromise the engineering solution.

The following section presents a case study on the performance of a pumping system, involving the analysis of parameters such as energy efficiency, response to variations in water demand, and pressure stability under different usage conditions. This research is expected to contribute to the development of more reliable and efficient pressurization systems, with applications in residential, commercial, and industrial environments, as well as to the implementation of Neutrosophy in improving and selecting a viable design.

3.2 Case study

The analysis focused on the evaluation of three main configurations: the conventional pressurization system (hydropneumatic tank with pressure switch: $\{V\}$), the system with presscontrol ($\{W\}$), and the integration of both devices into a single combined system ($\{VW\}$). For each of these configurations, fundamental parameters or selected pairs from the set $\{A_i\}$ were recorded, as defined in the following function:

$f\{E\} \rightarrow \{\{\text{flow rate}\}, \{\text{operating pressure}\}, \{\text{current intensity}\}, \{\text{voltage}\}\}, \{B_i\}, \{C_i\}, \{D_i\}$ according to the request defined in $\{E\}$. In fact, the client (residential, commercial, and industrial environments) requests the selection of the following pairs $\{V\}, \{W\}, \{VW\}$, with the aim of evaluating their performance and efficiency zones.

Another point to highlight in this study is that the information related to the sets $\{B_i\}, \{C_i\}, \{D_i\}$, is limited. Therefore, the neutrosophic degrees range from partially unknown to unknown and indeterminate. However, the impact on system selection is expected to show a favorable trend with respect to the economic variables $\{B_i\}$ (local electricity rates, installation costs, maintenance costs, and life cycle cost-benefit); environmental variables $\{C_i\}$: (availability and quality of the water resource); and contextual-operational variables $\{D_i\}$: (topology or distance of the residence from water reservoirs, comfort expectations, noise or autonomy, and variability in water demand).

3.2.1 Evaluation of parameters within the power set $\{A_i\}$

3.2.1.1 Performance curves of the evaluated pressurization systems

In order to experimentally validate the applied methodology and strengthen the comparative foundation of the study, the procedure was replicated using only the pump, without any control or pressurization elements. At this stage, a comparison was made between the performance curve provided by the manufacturer (catalog) and the performance curve obtained experimentally (see Figure 10). This comparison made it possible to verify the reliability of the measured data, ensuring that the graphs obtained in subsequent tests are properly aligned and accurately represent the real behavior of the system.

Figure 10: Performance curve of the INGCO UVPM3708 peripheral pump (v1: Catalog, v2: Pump). Source: own elaboration.

After conducting the corresponding tests, performance curves were obtained for each of the evaluated systems, as shown in Figure 11. Analyzing the curves for the pump and the presscontrol system reveals slight differences in flow rates between 0 and 0.5 m³/h. The curve with presscontrol starts at a head of approximately 39 m, whereas the pump without presscontrol registers a maximum value of 37.25 m. From medium flow rates between 0.8 and 2.0 m³/h, both curves tend to overlap, indicating that the hydraulic impact of the presscontrol becomes marginal. At flow rates near the maximum, the head converges toward values close to 6 m in both cases, demonstrating that the system maintains acceptable performance under high demand. This graph illustrates the effect of the presscontrol on the hydraulic performance of the pump, highlighting its influence under low-flow conditions and validating its efficiency within medium and high operating ranges. An average error of 0.86% was obtained, where it was observed that, when comparing the pump curve and the presscontrol curve, there was a deviation at low flow rates (0.1 to 0.4 cubic meters per hour), with the measured head being lower for the presscontrol system, yielding an error of 3.63%. For flow rates between 0.4 and 0.5 cubic meters per hour, the error was 1.53%.

Figure 11: Performance curves of the evaluated pressurization systems (v2: Pump, v3: Presscontrol, v4: Hydropneumatic, v5: Combined). Source: own elaboration.

On the other hand, the performance curve of the hydropneumatic system, compared to the behavior of the pump, shows a lower head at low flow rates, reaching approximately 37.25 m at 0.1 m³/h for the pump. In contrast, the hydropneumatic system starts with a lower value of 24.6 m for the same flow rate. This difference is attributed to the delay in the activation of the pressure switch and the damping effect of the tank. As the flow rate increases, both curves decrease progressively, indicating a reduction in available pressure. At the intersection point of both curves, around 0.9 m³/h and 18 m of head, hydraulic equilibrium between the pump and the hydropneumatic system is reached, at which point the impact of the system becomes minimal. Another relevant aspect of the analysis occurs at flow rates close to 2 m³/h, where both curves converge at an approximate head of 6 m, confirming that under high demand conditions, no significant losses occur. At this point, the relative error reaches a specific value of 3.44%, while the global average error of the system is only 0.37%, indicating good performance of the hydropneumatic system under medium and high flow regimes.

The comparison between the behavior of the pump and the combined system reveals that the pump delivers a head of 37.25 m at a flow rate of 0.13 m³/h, while the combined system reaches 27.41 m at a flow rate of 0.29 m³/h, reflecting a significant pressure loss similar to that of the hydropneumatic system. However, the combined system presents a higher head. As the flow rate increases, both curves tend to converge; around 0.9 m³/h, they intersect at an equilibrium point with a head of approximately 18 m, which may indicate the system’s optimal operating point. At higher flow rates, such as 1.9 m³/h, the difference between both curves is minimal: the pump delivers a head of 8 m, and the combined system, 7.7 m, corresponding to an error of 3.75%, with an average error of 0.63%. Overall, the average error along the entire curve is low, standing at 0.63%, which confirms the efficiency of the combined system in medium and high operating ranges.

3.2.1.2 Performance curves of the evaluated pressurization systems

Figure 12 presents the performance curve for each flow rate, showing that the INGCO 0.5 Hp pump exhibits a maximum efficiency of 20.35%, a minimum efficiency of 18.32%, and an efficient operating range between flow rates of 0.99 m³/h and 1.84 m³/h. Using the measured data from the hydropneumatic system, the performance curve was obtained (see Figure 13), with a maximum efficiency of 20.17%, a minimum efficiency of 18.15%, and an efficient operating range from a minimum flow rate of 1.25 m³/h

to a maximum flow rate of 1.88 m³/h for the hydropneumatic pressurization system to operate efficiently.

The performance curve of the system with a 0.5 HP pump and presscontrol, shown in Figure 14, exhibits a maximum efficiency of 22.48% and a minimum efficiency of 20.23%. From these data, the minimum and maximum flow rates for efficient system operation are determined as 1.02 m³/h and 1.86 m³/h, respectively. In contrast, Figure 15 presents the performance curve of the pressurization system combining the pump, hydropneumatic tank, and presscontrol, with a maximum efficiency of 21.62%, minimum efficiency of 19.46%, minimum flow rate of 1.09 m³/h, and maximum flow rate of 1.82 m³/h.

Figure 12: Performance curve of the 0.5 Hp pump, minimum efficiency, and flow rates of the efficient zone (v6: Efficiency, v7: Minimum efficiency, and v8: Polynomial (efficiency)). Source: own elaboration.

Figure 13: Performance curve of the hydropneumatic pressurization system, minimum efficiency, and flow rates of the efficient zone (v6: Efficiency, v7: Minimum efficiency, and v8: Polynomial (efficiency)). Source: own elaboration.

Figure 14: Performance curve of the pressurization system with pump and presscontrol, minimum efficiency, and flow rates of the efficient zone (v6: Efficiency, v7: Minimum efficiency, and v8: Polynomial (efficiency)). Source: own elaboration.

Figure 15: Performance curve of the system combining hydro-pneumatic tank and presscontrol, minimum efficiency, and flow rates at minimum efficiency (v6: Efficiency, v7: Minimum efficiency, and v8: Polynomial (efficiency)). Source: own elaboration.

3.2.1.3 Evaluation and comparison of flow rates within the operational efficiency zone

To determine the pressurization system with the best characteristics, a comparison was made between the operating flow rates within the maximum efficiency range of each analyzed configuration (Table 5). The evaluation was based on the minimum design flow rates required by various sanitary appliances according to the parameters established in Table 16.1 of the Ecuadorian Construction Standard NEC-11 (Ministry of Urban Development and Housing, 2011).

Table 5: Maximum and minimum flow rates within the efficient zone for the evaluated systems. Source: own elaboration.

System	Minimum Q (m ³ /h)	Maximum Q (m ³ /h)
Pump	0.99	1.84
Hydropneumatic	1.25	1.88
Presscontrol	1.02	1.86
Combined	1.09	1.82

Residential pressurization systems with a 0.5 Hp pump cover the demand of most sanitary appliances except for high-demand devices such as flushometer toilets, which require an instantaneous flow rate of 4.5 m³/h, and saunas, steam baths, or domestic hydromassage systems with a demand flow rate of 3.6 m³/h. However, for bidets, drinking fountains, tank toilets, and washbasins, which have a flow demand of 0.36 m³/h, as well as for urinals with valves requiring 0.54 m³/h, and for showers, kitchen sinks, hose faucets, washing machines, and dishwashers with a minimum instantaneous flow rate of 0.72 m³/h, the evaluated pressurization systems including the direct pump cover the demand. Nevertheless, these flow rates fall outside the efficient operating ranges, which were determined for each system in the performance curves. On the other hand, bathtubs, water heaters or boilers, and flushometer urinals, with a flow demand of 1.08 m³/h, are the only appliances within the efficient zone for two of the systems: direct pump and presscontrol (see Figures 16 and 17).

Figure 16: Performance curves of the pump and presscontrol with their efficient zones and sanitary appliance demand (1: Hydropneumatic, 2: Bathtub, 3: Bidet, 4: Boiler, 5: Shower, 6: Kitchen sink, 7: Hose bib, 8: Tank toilet, 9: Washbasin, 10: Washing machine, 11: Dishwasher, 12: Flush-valve urinal, 13: Manual-flush urinal, 14: Combined). Source: own elaboration.

Figure 17: Performance curves of the hydraulic system and combined system with their efficient zones and sanitary appliance demand (1: Hydropneumatic, 2: Bathtub, 3: Bidet, 4: Boiler, 5: Shower, 6: Kitchen sink, 7: Hose bib, 8: Tank toilet, 9: Washbasin, 10: Washing machine, 11: Dishwasher, 12: Flush-valve urinal, 13: Manual-flush urinal, 14: Combined). Source: own elaboration.

3.2 Discussion

The evaluation of parameters within the power set $\{A_i\}$ allowed the identification of the highest efficiency in $\{W\}$, followed by $\{VW\}$ and finally $\{V\}$, all intended for residential use when operated within their efficient zones. Therefore, the application of Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets in this study facilitated the evaluation of power sets based on the selection of parameter pairs for identifying water supply systems with greater efficiency. However, the study presents limitations related to the power sets $\{B_i\}, \{C_i\}, \{D_i\}$. Consequently, for the technical selection or evaluation of equipment and materials, it is necessary to determine whether the budget or financing covers installation, maintenance, and applicable electricity tariffs that the client may incur $\{B_i\}$. Additionally, an analysis of attributes measuring environmental impact $\{C_i\}$ should be performed by examining how waste generated relates to the volumes of water used [13]. Moreover, other parameters should be evaluated, such as the client’s satisfaction with the use of the optimally selected system $\{D_i\}$. Indeed, this indicates that $\{E\}$ does not always encompass the entirety or each specific requirement of the requesting user but rather depends on the neutrosophic membership degree of knowledge and experience of both the designer, evaluator, and the end client.

The study observed that the client’s state of desire $\{E\}$ enables the identification and grouping of the power sets to be evaluated. Specifically, the major parameter groups established in the power set $\{A_i\}$ were identified, where $\{\{disciplines\}, \{procurement\ and\ acquisition\}\}$ are noted. Consequently, the disciplines may consist of one, two, or multiple pairs of disciplines ($\{mechanical\}, \{automatic\}, \{hydraulic\}, \{processes\}, \{electrical\}$, among others), depending on the complexity of the structure, which is determined by $\{E\}$. In contrast, procurement and acquisition encompass the pairs $\{\{equipment\}, \{materials\}, \{equipment\ and\ materials\}\}$. The observable study identified from the power set $\{A_i\}$ the following pair: $\{\{hydraulic\}, \{processes\}\}, \{equipment\ and\ materials\}$. However, other disciplines are associated when implementing these systems in both residential and industrial areas, such as $\{architecture\}$ and less defined subcategories of $\{process\}$, including $\{\{corrosion\}, \{flows\}\}$. Similarly, it was observed that these attributes belonging to the power sets $\{B_i\}, \{C_i\}, \{D_i\}$ are defined, partially defined, or indeterminate according to the neutrosophic membership degree. Additionally, it

is proposed to conduct studies implementing these water supply systems in residential and industrial zones, as well as evaluating their technical, economic, and environmental viability by determining all implicit pairs of each power set [14].

4. Conclusion

The evaluation conducted through power sets and the application of Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets has made it possible to identify that the water supply systems with the highest performance for residential use are found in systems $\{W\}$ and $\{VW\}$, provided they operate within their efficient zone. Moreover, it has proven useful for comparing the energy and technical behavior of different systems by considering multiple disciplines and associated variables. In fact, the assessment of parameters in set $\{A_i\}$ has shown that the presscontrol primarily impacts low flow rates (0 to 0.5 m³/h), with up to 3.63% difference in head. From 0.8 m³/h onward, its effect becomes insignificant, with an average error of 0.86%, demonstrating good efficiency under medium and high domestic demand. Meanwhile, the hydropneumatic system shows lower initial head due to the pressure switch delay and tank effect, but it converges with the direct pump around 0.9 m³/h, with only 0.37% average error, indicating good performance at medium and high flow rates. On the other hand, it was observed that the combined system presents an initial pressure drop but maintains stable performance at high flow rates (1.9 m³/h), with an average error of 0.63%, confirming its efficiency under continuous consumption conditions.

The study has demonstrated that all the evaluated systems operate efficiently within their defined ranges, showing that the presscontrol system offers the highest performance (22.48%), followed by the combined system (21.62%) and the hydropneumatic system (20.17%). Although these systems do not meet the requirements of high-demand equipment, they are suitable for most common sanitary fixtures. Moreover, the evaluated systems show good performance within their specific flow rate ranges. However, limitations were identified in the sets $\{B_i\}$, $\{C_i\}$, $\{D_i\}$, related to economic, environmental, and user satisfaction aspects, due to the neutrosophic degree of membership of each power set. Consequently, this research has provided a useful methodological tool for the comprehensive analysis of water supply systems, and its application is proposed in case studies to validate its technical, economic, and environmental feasibility in residential and industrial settings.

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